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Gen C Learners' Issues: A Comparative Needs Assessment Analysis of the Needs of the Learners in the New Normal

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Abstract

The rise of global health risks, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has raised concerns about how people can protect themselves. The global financial crisis has exposed the many shortcomings in the education system. This includes the lack of adequate resources and supportive environments for learning. This descriptive-comparative research was participated in by 583 secondary and tertiary students from private and government school/universities who are currently undergoing the blended learning modality. The Students Counseling Needs Inventory (SCNI) by Patio (2014) was administered to determine the needs of the students aptly dubbed as Gen C. Gen C is a moniker for Generation COVID - a coined terminology for the learners who are experiencing the abrupt changes in the new normal education setting, brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicated a significant difference between the respondents' personal-social and spiritual needs. This disparity suggests that personal-social and spiritual needs are distinct and may not align uniformly across the entire spectrum of individual requirements. Also, it was shown that under blended learning, respondents feel shy to approach and meet other people and mostly, lack self-confidence. Data also revealed that they experience concerns about their relationship with their parents, with other people, and with themselves. Further, they are interested to know the possible jobs that they could pursue after college. Spiritually, despite the situation, they believe that they are blessed. The needs assessment output is intended to be the springboard for the formulation of a guidance program specifically designed to address these needs.

Keywords: *needs assessment, blended learning, tertiary students, secondary students, COVID-19 pandemic learning*

Introduction

Education has always been regarded as a stepping stone for a typical Filipino family to improve the standard of living. It is their ticket to becoming full-fledged, productive, relevant members of the Filipino society. Hence, the Education Sector is always an integral part of any government platform. It holds an unspoken claim to a vital seat on a nation's priority.

With the unexpected onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic, the education sector was among the critical areas that had to rapidly adapt to new challenges. According to a report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), nearly 90% of schools in the Philippines faced significant disruptions due to the pandemic, highlighting the urgent need for adjustments (PIDS, 2020). As Dr. Leonor Magtolis Briones, Secretary of the Department of Education (DepEd), noted, "The pandemic has pushed us to rethink our approach to education. We must innovate and adapt quickly to ensure that learning continues despite the challenges." Administrative leaders and teachers at various levels were forced to strategize and adopt necessary measures to mitigate the pandemic's impact on education. The shift to online learning, while crucial, exposed gaps in digital infrastructure and access. According to the National Center for Educational Statistics, over 30% of students in the Philippines lacked reliable internet access, posing a significant barrier to effective remote learning (NCES, 2021). Despite these obstacles, efforts to sustain educational quality persisted. As Professor Sylvia Concepcion, a leading education researcher, stated, "The resilience of our educators and students has been remarkable. They have shown that even in the face of unprecedented challenges, commitment to education remains unwavering." This commitment underscores the critical role of adaptability and resourcefulness in maintaining the quality of education for today's youth.

Through the DepEd Commons, online learning resources were launched to address the quarantine issues. Also, TV and radio solutions were also launched to address the lack of Internet access in certain areas. Parents and guardians were called on to support and assist the children in the so-called new normal learning. Synchronous and asynchronous learning activities, also known as blended learning were rapidly formulated by the educators. Students who have stable internet connections were categorized for online classes, and those who don't have gadgets and/or stable internet connection were sent modules of learning activities that they could accomplish at home sans the online lessons. Moreover, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) also came out with their own memorandum to all higher education institutions instructing them how to handle what they call Flexible Learning for tertiary education. Learners were categorized based on availability of devices, internet connectivity and level of digital literacy. Those who have no access to the internet and digital devices were put in the modular learning modality while those with internet connections were put in the blended learning modality.

The Education Sector seems to have formulated methods in the system and the technology needed, yet we ask, is this the entire viewpoint that the Sector has to look into? It is with this question in mind that this needs assessment survey and research for the learners of the new normal, which is entitled Gen-C Issues, was formulated. Gen C is a moniker for Generation COVID - a coined terminology for the learners who are experiencing the abrupt changes in the new normal education setting, brought about by the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Depression, stress, and loneliness were all reported to have worsened during the pandemic (Elmer, Mepham & Stadtfeld, 2020). Moreover, Nicholas Grubic (2020) mentioned that students also exhibited higher levels of anxiety.

With this, previous studies have suggested addressing the personal and social needs of the students. To address the inequalities between students, it is necessary to provide them with support that is focused on their holistic needs (Yorke et al., 2021). Saladino, Algeri, and Auriemma (2020) mentioned that the concept of monitoring and promoting the mental health of minors is suggested. Also, Lee (2020) noted that aside from the pandemic, there is also a need to study how long school closures and social distancing measures can affect the mental health of children and adolescents. It is important that children and adolescents are supported during this difficult time. Further, social support can help them manage their emotions and reduce their stress levels (Mosanya, 2020). Supporting students' ability to manage their emotions can help them deal with unforeseen circumstances (Yorke et al., 2021).

Research Questions

This research aimed to map out the challenges being experienced by the said learners in a holistic way. It aimed to look into, identify, and compare their needs in the following categories: personal and social needs, career and academic needs, self-esteem needs, and spiritual needs. Through determining the needs of the students in each dimension, the researchers will develop an intervention program that will support, motivate, and encourage students to live positively and fruitfully during these times.

Literature Review

Due to this pandemic and the closure of educational institutions, the number of students who are required to stay at home is large. The pandemic had a big impact on the student's experience of both work and life, e.g., from face-to-face discussion to online schooling, different methods of learning, different evaluation methods, etc., and their social life, e.g., no meeting with classmates and friends, no parties, etc.

The transition from face-to-face to online learning happened very quickly, giving the universities a little time to prepare. The effectiveness of online learning lies not just with the teachers but also with the students and the resources (e.g., internet connection, availability of computers, computer literacy of the students, etc.) In one global study, developing nations in Asia and Africa lagged behind when it came to video conferences and recordings (Aristovnik et al., 2020).

Students are at high risk for developing mental health concerns during this time. In the study of Son et al. (2020), it is important that they are equipped with the necessary tools to manage their mental health. Concerns about their own health and the well-being of their loved ones were also highlighted. Many students were worried about their progress due to the restrictions on social interaction and research.

The self-esteem of the students has a significant factor in educational success. Self-esteem and confidence are correlated. Therefore, when a student has a healthy self-esteem they tend to be confident. The parents and the educators have a role in building self-esteem and confidence which will ensure a good atmosphere in learning. If a student loses confidence in school, his or her grades might be affected and give up on his or her plans, dreams, and hopes. Students may feel that they are not worthy and think that it is impossible to achieve their goals. Establishing self-esteem in students can help in preventing attrition and assist students in achieving their dreams as well as pursuing college-level (EduNova Co., 2012)

One of the most important psychological health indicators is self-esteem. It is dynamic and influences various aspects of an individual's life (Gencer, 2021). Research shows that self-esteem is related to better grades and adjustments to college. Other researches revealed that self-esteem is a result of achievement. Having high self-esteem is beneficial, but it has negative consequences. The negative consequences are maladaptive strategies such as being aggressive, belittling others, ignoring negative feedback, taking less responsibility (Wasylikiw et al., 2021).

The pandemic has created new stressors for individuals with mental health conditions such as fear and worry. It can also affect their physical health. Mental health issues can affect academic success. It can also affect social interactions and motivation for students.

Studies show that people who are more spiritual are more likely to have good mental health. They even show that spiritual beliefs and practices can improve a person's well-being. Certain beliefs and rituals are often used to manage illness and other life changes. The physiological effects of spiritual beliefs on physical health have been studied. They have been linked to various diseases and disorders (Koenig, 2012).

The PACSSS (Personal, Academic, Career, Social, Self-Esteem, and Spiritual) Model that focuses on enhancing student development and success in a crisis was employed as the framework of this study. COVID-19 has brought so many struggles to individuals of any age. Students are reporting increased difficulty focusing on their studies due to the added stress and worry caused by the various platforms used for distance learning (Lewison, 2020).

The needs assessment output shall be the springboard for the formulation of a guidance program specifically formulated to address these needs. This research aligns itself with the University's research priority on Community Responsiveness which aims to produce research on identification of problems and needs of different communities, focusing on the creation of programs and generation of

products (material and human) and services that are crucial for the communities' subsistence and survival. As was aforementioned, the COVID-19 onslaught sent nations reeling at its wake, with all government sectors fighting to steady themselves while still others still figuring out how to get back on their feet. Among the major sectors needing to make big and abrupt adjustments is the Education Sector. The learners of the present season, mostly belonging to the Gen Z category whose age bracket is 13-23 years old, still falls in the emotionally developing stage. Their generation is likewise characterized by a highly interactive nature regardless if it's in person or online interaction.

The constrictions brought about by the season might not be solely confined to academic needs but might span the personal, social, emotional and spiritual needs. Holistic address of these issues is necessary to help these learners cope with the current situation. It is with this presumption that the researchers, in line with the Community Responsiveness research agenda, desire to contribute to the perceived needs of a vital member of the community - those we dubbed Gen C - the learners of the pandemic generation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study made use of descriptive-comparative research design. Descriptive statistics were then computed to describe the sample's characteristics. The statistics obtained from the secondary students were compared with the tertiary students using t-test.

Participants

Five hundred eighty-three (583) students from public and private schools and universities were the respondents in this particular study. To ensure a representative sample, stratified random sampling was employed. This method allowed the researchers to capture the diverse perspectives of different educational levels and institutions. Three hundred twenty-two (322) of the respondents were tertiary students from private and public institutions and universities in Metro Manila and Pampanga, while the remaining 261 were secondary students from a private institution in Metro Manila. All participants were attending classes under the blended learning modality, providing a comprehensive view of the current educational landscape during the pandemic.

Instrument

Students Counseling Needs Inventory (SCNI)

This study adopted the Students Counseling Needs Inventory (SCNI), which consists of 48 items that assess various concerns and needs of the students. All responses are given using a five-point Likert scale (1-Never, 2-Seldom, 3-Sometimes, 4-Most of the time, 5-All the time). This questionnaire assesses and measures personal and social needs (26 items), career and academic needs (10 items), self-esteem needs (6 items), and spiritual needs (6 items) of a student's life. The instrument covered ages 12-18. This test was developed by Janice Dee Patio (2014). The SCNI internal consistency is 0.90 which means it is acceptable enough since a high value of alpha (above 0.90) (Tavakol, 2011; Streiner & Norman, 1989) signifies that the test is reliable in measuring the counseling needs of the students. The test was validated by five experts in this field and they further testified that this instrument does measure student counseling needs. Some items were modified to suit the tertiary learners. After the pilot testing of the SCNI to tertiary learners, its internal consistency was measured using Cronbach Alpha. The test yielded to 0.919 which indicates excellent internal consistency.

Procedure

For the secondary level, the general objectives of this study, along with the benefits to be gained, were presented to the school administrators where the study is to be conducted. The secondary students were given consent forms to be signed by their parents, affirming their participation in the study. Respondents and their parents were assured of the confidentiality of information. During the administration of the test, the researchers did it by class through Zoom App to ensure the breach of confidentiality.

For the tertiary level, the needs assessment survey form was posted in the social media accounts and were also sent through the social messaging sites of the researchers, taking into careful consideration the necessary measures to ensure the confidentiality of the responses and identity of the students. Interested respondents were sent the google form links to the survey assessment questionnaire which likewise provided online consent forms where they signify their willingness to participate in the study.

The responses of the students were tallied using a spreadsheet. Data gathered are presented in frequency and percentage distribution tables. Quantitative data were studied through the usage of the statistical program, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 25). A T-test was employed to compare the needs assessment analysis of the learners' needs in the new normal. This statistical method allowed for the evaluation of differences between the means of two independent groups, ensuring a robust comparison of the collected data. The results from the T-test provided significant insights into the varying needs of learners adapting to the new educational modalities.

From these results, the researchers shall develop a guidance program to address the needs that emerged. It should be noted, however, that only those items which elicited the answers Seldom, Sometimes, Most of the Time, and All the Time are to be analyzed and interpreted except in items which required reversed scoring.

Ethical Considerations

One of the most important factors that can be considered when it comes to protecting autonomy is implementing an informed consent process. This method allowed the potential participants to be fully informed about the study's purpose and benefits. The Belmont Report states that humans should be treated with respect and deference. This means that the researcher followed ethical guidelines when conducting the study.

Before starting the study, every potential participant was asked to provide informed consent. This form of consent included all of the necessary details about the study, such as its purpose and possible risks.

The Statement of the Problem clearly stated the various steps that were taken to protect the confidentiality and anonymity of the study's participants. The researchers utilized different techniques to prevent the unauthorized access to the data collected from them. In addition, it clearly stated the respondents' rights and provided contact details.

When they read their consent, the potential participants were given an opportunity to ask the researcher questions. The study's participants merely wrote their names and signatures on the form, which linked them to the investigation.

After collecting the necessary information about the study's participants, the researcher then carried out an assessment of the possible risks and benefits associated with the project. This step was carried out using the guidance of Wendler and Rid. The researchers then used the collected data to come up with a better solution.

The concept of Right to Justice ensures that the study's participants are aware that it will address their concerns. It also allows them to benefit from the results.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. As can be seen, a total of five hundred eighty-three (583) students were the participants of this study. Two hundred sixty-one (261) were secondary students while three hundred twenty-two (322) were tertiary students. For the secondary students: one hundred fifty-one (57.9%) of them were aged 15 followed by 78 (29.9%) who were 16 years old. All of the secondary student respondents were male (n=261) and were studying as Grade 10 students in a private school. For the tertiary students: one hundred two (31.68%) of them were aged 19 followed by 84 (26.09%) who were 20 years old. Eighty-one (25.16%) were aged 18. Majority (n=238; 73.91%) of the respondents were females. While 84 or 26.09% were males. Most of them (n=267; 82.92%) were studying in government or state universities. A few (n=55; 17.08%) were enrolled in a private university. In terms of year level, 140 (43.48%) were in first year, 109 (33.85%) were in second year and 73 (22.67%) were in third year.

Table 1. *Respondents' Profile*

Baseline Characteristics	Tertiary		Secondary	
	f	%	f	%
<i>Age</i>				
13	0	0	1	0.4
14	0	0	15	5.7
15	0	0	151	57.9
16	0	0	78	29.9
17	0	0	15	5.7
18	81	25.16	1	0.4
19	102	31.68	0	0
20	84	26.09	0	0
21	37	11.49	0	0
22	7	2.17	0	0
23	1	0.31	0	0
24	2	0.62	0	0
25	1	0.31	0	0
Others	7	2.17	0	0
<i>Sex</i>				
Female	238	73.91	0	0
Male	84	26.09	261	100
<i>Nature of school</i>				
Government/State University	267	82.92	0	0
Private	55	17.08	261	100
<i>Grade/Year Level</i>				
Grade 10	0	0	261	100
First	140	43.48	0	0
Second	109	33.85	0	0
Third	73	22.67	0	0

Table 2. Respondents' Self-Esteem Needs

Self-Esteem Needs	5		4		3		2		1		Total		5		4		3		2		1		Total	
	(All the Time)		(Most of the Time)		(Sometimes)		(Seldom)		(Never)		f %		(All the Time)		(Most of the Time)		(Sometimes)		(Seldom)		(Never)		f %	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
5. I am shy to approach other people.	39	12.11	105	32.61	123	38.2	41	12.73	14	4.35	322	100	37	14.18	62	23.75	100	38.31	47	18.01	15	5.75	261	100
6. I don't want to join clubs/organization in school.	34	10.56	55	17.08	123	38.2	65	20.19	45	13.98	322	100	23	8.81	46	17.62	105	40.23	52	19.92	35	13.41	261	100
19. I don't know what course to take in college.	13	4.04	37	11.49	90	27.95	78	24.22	104	32.3	322	100	27	10.34	44	16.86	73	27.97	60	22.99	57	21.84	261	100
26. I am not comfortable in meeting people.	20	6.21	52	16.15	122	37.89	80	24.84	48	14.91	322	100	9	3.45	37	14.18	82	31.42	79	30.27	54	20.69	261	100
35. I lack self-confidence.	68	21.12	70	21.74	122	37.89	44	13.66	18	5.59	322	100	40	15.33	56	21.46	80	30.65	50	19.16	35	13.41	261	100
45. I am confused about what I want to do.	51	15.84	85	26.4	128	39.75	38	11.8	20	6.21	322	100	39	14.94	51	19.54	83	31.80	61	23.37	27	10.34	261	100

Table 2 shows the self-esteem needs of the respondents. As can be seen, one hundred twenty-three or 38.20% of the tertiary students while 38.31 of the secondary students indicated that they sometimes feel shy to approach other people. One hundred five or 32.61% of the tertiary students and sixty-two or 23.75 % of the secondary students expressed that they experience this most of the time which only means that secondary students are more approachable compare to tertiary students. Thirty-four or 10.56 % of participants from tertiary level while 23 or 8.81 % from secondary level do not want to join school organizations. Moreover, 65 or 20.19% seldom participate in clubs for tertiary level and 52 or 13.41 for secondary level. This implies that self-esteem is not stable; it depends on the events that an individual encounter, it might fluctuate but it can be developed. Students with high self-esteem have a significant impact on well-being and enhance the capacity of the students to maintain a healthy relationship with others. Low self-esteem can make it difficult for people with low self-esteem to defend their opinions (Darjan, Negru and Ilie, 2020).

High self-esteem is linked to better mental health. It is also associated with academic achievement and willingness to express oneself. However, low self-esteem has a significant relationship to alcoholism, drugs, poor mental health, abuse, and crime. Self-esteem matters to everyone. Self-esteem has positive effects and benefits particularly to high school students (Sheykhjan, Jabari and Rajeswari, 2014). Addressing the problem of the students who are seeking help, encouraging them, and assisting them to increase their self-esteem is beneficial in many ways. Self-esteem is significant in pre-college schooling which will help in the adjustment and preparation of students going college. It also shows that the higher the student's self-esteem, the more likely they are to attend college (Torres, 2007).

Self-esteem continues to develop and increase in both youth and middle age as long as the individual's physical and cognitive abilities remain intact. Therefore, self-esteem is significant to the school-age of students especially to high school and college level (Orth and Robbins, 2014). Also, the research of Cudjoe and Sarfo (2019) shows that the use of group activities like assertive training in school boost and improve the self-esteem in both primary and secondary level of students.

Table 3, on the next page, displays the personal-social needs of the students. As can be seen, both secondary and tertiary students have concerns about their relationship with their parents, with other people, and with themselves. This implies that in terms of their relationship with their parents, students have been experiencing the difficulty of telling their problems to their parents (secondary students = 26.82%; tertiary students = 32.51%) because of the fear that they might not understand them (secondary students = 27.20%; tertiary students = 30.65%).

In terms of their relationship with other people, students have feelings of uneasiness towards their classmates (secondary students = 35.25%; tertiary students = 31.58%) and that their classmates do not like them (secondary students = 49.43%; tertiary students = 38.08%). With these kinds of concerns, they assume that some people are making rumors about them and that there are people that are against them (secondary students = 37.16%; tertiary students = 36.84%).

In continuation, in terms of their relationship towards themselves, students have been experiencing trouble sleeping at night (secondary students = 24.52%; tertiary students = 30.03%) and having a difficulty of getting enough sleep (secondary students = 29.12%; tertiary students = 28.79%). Moreover, students have also answered that they do not like their physical appearance or the way their face register in the screen (secondary students = 33.33%; tertiary students = 39.94%), have difficulty controlling their temper (secondary students = 36.78%; tertiary students = 25.39%), have feelings of being scared (secondary students = 28.35%; tertiary students = 20.43%), have trouble in overcoming painful memories (secondary students = 31.03%; tertiary students = 31.27), feelings of being tired (secondary students = 37.55%; tertiary students = 37.46%), and suffers from headache (secondary students = 25.29%; tertiary students = 38.08%). Students have also feelings of being alone (secondary students = 34.48%; tertiary students = 38.08%); feelings of worthlessness (secondary students = 33.33%; tertiary students = 37.46%); feelings of being neglected (secondary students = 27.59%; tertiary students = 37.46%); and feelings of being unhappy (secondary students = 42.15%; tertiary students = 48.92%).

Table 3. Respondents' Personal-Social Needs

Personal - Social Needs	TERTIARY STUDENTS										SECONDARY STUDENTS													
	5 (All the Time)		4 (Most of the Time)		3 (Sometimes)		2 (Seldom)		1 (Never)		Total	5 (All the Time)		4 (Most of the Time)		3 (Sometimes)		2 (Seldom)		1 (Never)		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
3. I cannot control my temper.	10	3.10	52	16.10	161	49.85	82	25.39	17	5.26	322	100	6	2.30	37	14.18	88	33.72	96	36.78	34	13.03	261	100
4. I am unhappy.	12	3.72	56	17.34	158	48.92	80	24.77	16	4.95	322	100	8	3.07	28	10.73	110	42.15	91	34.87	24	9.20	261	100
7. My classmate don't like me.	4	1.24	20	6.19	81	25.08	123	38.08	94	29.10	322	100	4	1.53	9	3.45	59	22.61	129	49.43	60	22.99	261	100
8. I don't get enough sleep.	59	18.27	93	28.79	120	37.15	40	12.38	10	3.10	322	100	47	18.01	76	29.12	86	32.95	40	15.33	12	4.60	261	100
9. I feel neglected.	18	5.57	40	12.38	121	37.46	96	29.72	47	14.55	322	100	7	2.68	20	7.66	72	27.59	80	30.65	82	31.42	261	100
10. I feel scared.	33	10.22	66	20.43	118	36.53	65	20.12	40	12.38	322	100	13	4.98	17	6.51	74	28.35	77	29.50	80	30.65	261	100
11. I want to run away from home.	14	4.33	44	13.62	67	20.74	60	18.58	137	42.41	322	100	5	1.92	7	2.68	40	15.33	48	18.39	161	61.69	261	100
12. My parents favor my siblings over me.	10	3.10	25	7.74	75	23.22	75	23.22	137	42.41	322	100	6	2.30	15	5.75	42	16.09	47	18.01	151	57.85	261	100
13. My parents do not understand me.	12	3.72	48	14.86	99	30.65	76	23.53	87	26.93	322	100	18	6.90	28	10.73	71	27.20	70	26.82	74	28.35	261	100
18. My parents don't trust me.	9	2.79	24	7.43	90	27.86	79	24.46	120	37.15	322	100	14	5.36	21	8.06	54	20.69	83	31.80	89	34.10	261	100
20. I don't like my physical appearance / the way my face register in the screen.	21	6.50	58	17.96	129	39.94	57	17.65	57	17.65	322	100	18	6.90	36	13.79	87	33.33	73	27.97	47	18.01	261	100
21. I am not comfortable with my classmates.	10	3.10	27	8.36	102	31.58	97	30.03	86	26.63	322	100	5	1.92	21	8.06	60	22.99	92	35.25	83	31.80	261	100
24. I have trouble in overcoming painful memories.	55	17.03	82	25.39	101	31.27	60	18.58	24	7.43	322	100	31	11.88	55	21.07	81	31.03	65	24.90	29	11.11	261	100
25. I have thought of ending my life.	13	4.02	35	10.84	78	24.15	67	20.74	129	39.94	322	100	11	4.21	16	6.13	37	14.18	70	26.82	127	48.66	261	100
27. I am always tired.	43	13.31	77	23.84	121	37.46	63	19.5	18	5.57	322	100	35	13.41	45	17.24	98	37.55	65	24.90	18	6.90	261	100
29. I want to hurt myself.	12	3.72	26	8.05	67	20.74	73	22.64	144	44.58	322	100	3	1.15	10	3.83	27	10.34	60	22.99	161	61.69	261	100
30. I cry at night.	30	9.29	61	18.89	109	33.75	72	22.29	50	15.48	322	100	7	2.68	18	6.90	48	18.39	67	25.67	121	46.36	261	100
31. I have trouble sleeping.	53	16.41	83	25.70	97	30.03	57	17.65	32	9.91	322	100	37	14.18	41	15.71	60	22.99	64	24.52	59	22.61	261	100
32. I cannot tell my problems to my parents.	105	32.51	79	24.46	72	22.29	40	12.38	26	8.05	322	100	51	19.54	39	14.94	70	26.82	55	21.07	46	17.62	261	100
33. I suffer from headaches.	35	10.84	60	18.58	123	38.08	78	24.15	23	8.05	322	100	16	6.13	26	9.96	66	25.29	79	30.27	74	28.35	261	100
34. I feel that people are against me.	21	6.50	40	12.38	119	36.84	76	23.53	66	20.43	322	100	9	3.45	23	8.81	64	24.52	97	37.16	68	26.05	261	100
37. I am nobody.	53	16.41	92	28.48	123	38.08	37	11.46	17	5.26	322	100	23	8.81	43	16.48	90	34.48	65	25.29	39	14.94	261	100
38. Some people are making rumors about me.	10	3.10	34	10.53	119	36.84	90	27.86	69	21.36	322	100	6	2.30	14	5.36	52	19.92	81	31.03	108	41.38	261	100
39. I am not close with my parents.	13	4.02	37	11.46	84	26.01	74	22.91	114	35.29	322	100	8	3.07	15	5.75	45	17.24	71	27.20	122	46.74	261	100
42. I feel worthless.	25	7.74	45	13.93	121	37.46	66	20.43	65	20.12	322	100	13	4.98	16	6.13	50	19.16	87	33.33	95	36.40	261	100
43. I want to hurt someone.	3	0.93	10	3.10	38	11.76	52	16.1	219	67.80	322	100	8	3.07	10	3.83	30	11.49	43	16.48	170	65.13	261	100

It implies that college students should encourage the value of parent-child interactions in order to support their development (Waithaka, Furniss, & Gitimu, 2017). Fathers who are more engaged with their children are more likely to be happy and feel valued by them. They are also more likely to maintain a close relationship with their children due to their family's origin. The importance of attachment bond among a mother and her infant is acknowledged by various experts. This concept is associated with a number of developmental benefits, such as lower rates of depression and better peer relationships.

Students tend to learn more when their peers are supporting them. This is because it helps them develop their own ideas and opinions. If a student does not get along with his or her peers, it can affect their grades at the end of the semester. The positive relationships between students help them feel valued and included in school. (Stefa, 2018).

Connectedness is an overarching concept that describes students' sense of belongingness and their integration with their institution. Students may feel connected to other students through social groups and relationships. They also develop connectedness to their institution through acceptance and belonging to various programs and organizations. High social connectedness is associated with a host of positive health and well-being outcomes. While, a lack of social connectedness can cause depression, social anxiety, and jealousy. A sense of belonging and community are influenced by a student's perception of themselves and their peers. A high-quality social life also contributes to a sense of belonging. (Jorgenson, Farrell, Fudge, & Pritchard, 2018).

Table 4, on the next page, shows the career-academic needs of the respondents. Majority of the tertiary students notably answered that they are aware of the importance of education, 240 (74.53%). In connection with this, 163 (50.62%) indicated that all the time, students submit their projects on the set deadline and 162 (50.31%) are aware that having good grades will help them in choosing the right course. This indicates that despite this pandemic, they still put importance and value to education.

Moreover, 41.30% (all the time) and 38.51% (most of the time) of the respondents exert their efforts in their studies. Results likewise yielded that 29.50% of the students' desire to choose and have desired to choose (for those who have already entered college) on what university is right for them.

In terms of their career and academic needs, 69 (21.43%) want to know more about the different courses in college. In addition, 145 (45.03 %) of the respondents want to know if their skills, interest, and abilities can help in choosing the right course. Lastly, 172 (53.42 %) of the respondents are interested to know the possible jobs that they could get after taking their course in college.

On one hand, the secondary students similar to the tertiary students knew that having good grades will help them choose in the right academic strand, 180 (68.97%) and majority of them also know the importance of education, 166 (63.60%).

As can be seen in Table 4, in the next page, in terms of academic and career needs, 150 (57.47%) would like to know their skills and interests, and abilities can help them choose the right academic strand. Moreover, 162 (62.07%) want to know the possible jobs that they could get in the academic strand they will be taking. Also, they would like to prepare themselves for the career they will be choosing, 162 (62.07%).

Table 4. Respondents' Career-Academic Needs

Career/Academic Needs	TERTIARY STUDENTS											SECONDARY STUDENTS												
	5		4		3		2		1		Total	5		4		3		2		1		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
2. I submit my school projects on time	163	50.62	124	38.51	29	9.01	2	0.62	4	1.24	322	100.00	111	42.53	122	46.74	26	9.96	2	0.77	0	0.00	261	100
14. I want to choose on which school/university is right for me.	95	29.50	71	22.05	73	22.67	41	12.73	42	13.04	322	100.00	164	62.84	66	25.29	26	9.96	3	1.15	2	0.77	261	100
15. I exert my best effort in my studies.	133	41.30	124	38.51	53	16.46	10	3.11	2	0.62	322	100.00	59	22.61	133	50.96	62	23.75	5	1.92	2	0.77	261	100
16. I am aware of the importance of education to my future.	240	74.53	63	19.57	12	3.73	4	1.24	3	0.93	322	100.00	166	63.60	75	28.74	15	5.75	3	1.15	2	0.77	261	100
17. I want to prepare myself for a new career.	188	58.39	100	31.06	28	8.70	4	1.24	2	0.62	322	100.00	162	62.07	72	27.59	21	8.05	3	1.15	3	1.15	261	100
40. I want to know if my skills, interest and abilities can help me choose the right course.	145	45.03	108	33.54	58	18.01	8	2.48	3	0.93	322	100.00	150	57.47	84	32.18	19	7.28	8	3.07	0	0.00	261	100
41. I want to know the possible jobs that I could get in the course that I would be taking.	172	53.42	104	32.30	38	11.80	4	1.24	4	1.24	322	100.00	162	62.07	75	28.74	21	8.05	3	1.15	0	0.00	261	100
46. I want to know more about the different courses in college academic strand in college/SHS	69	21.43	75	23.29	117	36.34	43	13.35	18	5.59	322	100.00	113	43.30	85	32.57	52	19.92	11	4.21	0	0.00	261	100
47. I know that the grades I am getting could affect my course choice in college/SHS.	131	40.68	106	32.92	68	21.12	14	4.35	3	0.93	322	100.00	171	65.52	66	25.29	22	8.43	2	0.77	0	0.00	261	100
48. I am aware that having good grades will help me in choosing the right course/academic strand.	162	50.31	95	29.50	52	16.15	9	2.80	4	1.24	322	100.00	180	68.97	62	23.75	19	7.28	0	0.00	0	0.00	261	100

According to Trinidad and Leviste (2020), higher education has various functions that are critical to the country's development. Academic motivation is a concept that relates to increased levels of achievement (Ajayi et al., 2012). Based on the study of Crede and Kuncel (2008), good study behaviors cover taking notes in class, joining the class discussions, reviewing materials, submitting projects on time while poor study behaviors are skipping class, not complying with the assignments, and excessive time spent watching television and using their electronic gadgets. Linderman (2010) argued that knowing the motivations of students can help in formulating strategies that can improve their academic performance.

When it comes to career, goals play a significant part in shaping the behavior of the individual in higher education because it leads students to achieve excellence in academics (Lopez-Bonilla et al., 2012). According to the study, students' career goals are associated with four career behaviors, which are considered proactive career behaviors by counselors (Clements & Kamau, 2018). In 2011, Schoon and Polek argued that students with high academic and career goals are more likely to succeed academically and professionally. Moreover, it was also stated that students who choose their program in college and have a clear reason why they pursue it tend to have a better outcome in terms of academic achievement (Adeokun & Opoko, 2015).

Table 5. Respondents' Spiritual Needs

Spiritual Needs	TERTIARY STUDENTS										SECONDARY STUDENTS													
	5 (All the Time)		4 (Most of the Time)		3 (Sometimes)		2 (Seldom)		1 (Never)		Total	5 (All the Time)		4 (Most of the Time)		3 (Sometimes)		2 (Seldom)		1 (Never)		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
1. I don't know how to exercise my faith.	15	4.66	33	10.25	127	39.44	81	25.16	66	20.50	322	100	9	3.45	38	14.56	87	33.33	79	30.27	48	18.39	261	100
22. I am blessed.	210	65.22	56	17.39	40	12.42	12	3.73	4	1.24	322	100	127	48.66	90	34.48	33	12.64	7	2.68	4	1.53	261	100
23. I have strong faith in God	202	62.73	54	16.77	39	12.11	18	5.59	9	2.80	322	100	113	43.30	81	31.03	41	15.71	14	5.36	12	4.60	261	100
28. I follow God's commandments.	83	25.78	119	36.96	92	28.57	23	7.14	5	1.55	322	100	63	24.14	103	39.46	78	29.89	9	3.45	8	3.07	261	100
36. I pray before I take an exam	135	41.93	78	24.22	71	22.05	25	7.76	13	4.04	322	100	74	28.35	67	25.67	49	18.77	39	14.94	32	12.26	261	100
44. I pray everyday	149	46.27	70	21.74	58	18.01	33	10.25	12	3.73	322	100	81	31.03	46	17.62	56	21.46	52	19.92	26	9.96	261	100

As seen in Table 5, 210 (65.22%) of the respondents in the tertiary level answered that they are blessed even if there are 4 (1.24 %) of the respondents who don't know how to exercise their faith. On the other hand, 127 (48.66%) in the secondary level answered that they are also blessed as opposed to the 48 (18.39 %) who also do not know how to exercise their faith.

Moreover, 202 (62.73%) of the respondents in the tertiary level responded that they have a strong faith in God as compared to the (43.30%) or 113 of the secondary level student respondents. Lastly, three percent (3%) of the tertiary level and twelve percent (12%) in the secondary level answered that they do not pray before an examination.

Spirituality is a dynamic and integral aspect of humanity. Individuals who seek to have ultimate meaning and purpose in life (Puchalski, Vitillo, Hull and Reller, 2014). It also seeks to develop a deep connection with others. Different cultures have their own interpretations of spirituality.

Wood and Hilton (2012) stated that students' spiritual connections are very important in helping them overcome their obstacles. Although in the study of Wood and Hilton (2012), the study focused on how spirituality helped overcome various situations, it did not discuss specific situations where it helped them overcome. Apparently, spirituality made students well-adjusted to survive the academic community (Cox, 2011; Wood and Hilton, 2012). Most students admitted that their God or deity served as their confidantes with whom they can share their issues. Furthermore, the students shared that spirituality inspired them to succeed while for others, it enabled them to get through academic challenges and reduced relational distractions.

Table 6. Comparative Analysis of Respondents' Needs

	Personal and Social Needs		Career and Academics Needs		Self-Esteem Needs		Spiritual Needs		Overall Needs	
	Secondary	Tertiary	Secondary	Tertiary	Secondary	Tertiary	Secondary	Tertiary	Secondary	Tertiary
Mean	3.65	3.34	4.17	4.14	3.02	2.99	3.66	3.97	3.68	3.54
SD	0.681	0.681	0.347	0.555	0.788	0.744	0.712	0.776	0.465	0.486
t-value		5.340		.899		3.88		-5.044		3.417
p-value		0.000		0.369		0.698		0.000		0.001

Table 6 displays the comparative analysis of the respondents' needs. Data revealed that the mean score of personal and social needs of secondary students is 3.65 with an SD of 0.68 while 3.34 is the mean score for the tertiary and 0.68 SD resulted a significant difference. Moreover, the mean score of the spiritual needs of the secondary is 3.66 with 0.71 SD while the mean score for tertiary is 3.97 with 0.77 SD, the spirituality needs resulting in a p-value of 0.00 which means a significant difference is revealed. Concerning the career and academics, the secondary level gained a mean score of 4.17 with an SD of 0.35 while the tertiary obtained a mean score of 4.14 and SD of 0.55. Furthermore, the mean score of self-esteem needs of the secondary is 3.02 with an SD of 0.78 and the mean score of tertiary level is 2.99 with an SD of 0.74. The results show that career, academics, and self-esteem have no significant difference between the high school and tertiary levels. Moreover, overall results revealed a significant difference to the needs of secondary and tertiary students.

According to Baker (2012) and Fowler (1981), as cited by Milstein and Manierre (2012), as a person grows older thru the different lifespan, it changes from unreflective personal quest for meaning to an expansion of being a self-reflective individual. In the quest of meaning, the young person is more likely to group like others and develop ideas that fit with others, which will help them later in life. Adolescent's spirituality ages 10-19 years old (secondary students) as described from Fowler's Stages of Faith and Selfhood (1981), as cited by Milstein and Manierre (2012), called this stage as interpersonal self, wherein there is a need to integrate various self-images in order to form a coherent identity. At this stage, they do not believe in the existence of a belief system. They may start to question their beliefs. They may also start to adopt a lifestyle that is contrary to their former faith.

As cited by Buijs (2020), Social need fulfilment has been linked to physical health and social resources. Social needs and their fulfilment may, therefore, also differ over the life course following normative social role transitions. Social needs and their fulfillment may also change over time following the transition from a social role to a non-normative one (Wong, Hall, Justice and Hernandez, 2015). They even added that young people can now fully think logically. They begin to want a more logical explanation for everything. They begin

to value their peers more than their parents. They begin to listen to their peers' opinions. During their adolescent years, students are said to be developing their emotional and social competence. During these years, focus is on cultivating healthy, rewarding relationships that can help develop good communication skills and resolve conflicts.

This research has investigated the challenges being experienced by secondary and tertiary learners in a holistic way. It aimed to look into, identify and compare their needs in the following categories: personal and social needs; career and academic needs; self-esteem needs; and spiritual needs. Through determining the needs of the students in each dimension, the researchers intend to develop an intervention program that will support, motivate, and encourage students to live positively and fruitfully during these times. The study has shown that a significant difference is present between the respondents' personal and social needs ($p=0.000$), spiritual needs ($p=0.000$) and their needs as a whole ($p=0.001$). Also, it was shown that under blended learning, respondents feel shy to approach and meet other people and mostly, lack self-confidence. Data also revealed that they experience concerns about their relationship with their parents, with other people, and with themselves. Further, they are interested to know the possible jobs that they could pursue after college. Spiritually, despite the situation, they believe that they are blessed.

Findings in the present study are consistent with the findings of Chakma (2020) that no one is totally independent on this planet. People need the help of other beings to solve their problems. They want their wards to pursue their goals in life. The individual goes through various stages of development. There are various stages of development such as infancy, childhood, and adolescence. Many students face emotional problems due to various factors such as stress and tension. A good guidance program can help parents make informed decisions about their children's potentials. It is very important that the student receives proper guidance during his or her education.

Correspondingly, the engagement of students in various activities and groups contributed to their self-esteem and effectiveness in managing stress (Wassem, 2020). According to Farhan and Khan (2015), students from private institutions, colleges, and universities exhibited low stress and have higher self-esteem due to a flexible academic environment compared to the students in the public sector.

Self-esteem is connected to school performance which may lead to academic success or failure. Students with good performance in academics have high self-esteem tend to be self-effective and trust their abilities (Birkeland, Melkevkk, Holsen and Wold, 2012). Other studies showed that poor performance in academics has been related to feelings of ineffectiveness, failure, frustrations, and lack of expectations (Nieves, Alberto and Cortés, 2020). In line with this, developing self-esteem is one of the most important factors for academic success (Hyseni and Hoxha, 2018). Self-esteem activities are excellent ways for students to boost their self-confidence and increase motivation in learning (EduNova Co., 2012).

On the other hand, the decisions that students make at school have a huge impact on their lives. They affect their social lives and health outcomes. According to Moriya (2011), in today's world, careers are becoming more defined as being constructed through a series of choices that students make throughout their education and careers. She also emphasized the importance of supporting children in making informed choices.

There are similarities between the present study and those described by Blankstein (2020). According to her, many students struggle with balancing their academic and personal responsibilities. She added that students often have to borrow money to cover their basic needs. Many students face significant challenges outside of the classroom. These difficulties can have a significant impact on their academic success.

These findings also suggest that as students' progress up the pyramid, they must have their spiritual and religious communities satisfied at their individual level (Kroth 2007). Self-actualization is the process of moving from one need to the next (Maslow, 1964). Religious beliefs and rituals could very well play a huge role in the success of students. Sherwin and Stevenson (2010) specified that when social needs are not met, religion and spirituality can be devastating to students. They added that educating students about their religious beliefs is an important aspect of ensuring that they are fulfilled.

Conclusions

Education leaders and parents need to have a broad view of the students in order to maintain the proper monitoring and improvement of their schools. As what was taken up in the result and discussion of this research, the various aspects of the students' well-being - self-esteem, personal and social, academic and career, and the spiritual - stays the same regardless of the season. It just revolves around different methods, but still highly needs guidance and support.

It is therefore the hope of the researchers of this study that this shall be used as take-off point in furthering guidance and intervention programs for the betterment of the studentry.

An important issue emerging from these findings is the demographic profile of the respondents. Due to time constraints, in the aspect of the secondary student respondents, researchers were able to acquire data only from an all boy school and in one particular grade level. It should also be noted that the number of respondents should also be equal across all grade levels.

This assessment survey of the Gen-C's needs during this new normal set-up of learning provides significant data to help provide a take-off point in formulating an intervention program. Though not specifically pointing out that these needs are brought about by the current circumstances, the needs assessment result shows that the needs identified in this study are significant to the students regardless of the

situation. Leading indicators related to student well-being, could help in student engagement, and improving the conditions for learning in the current normal. This entire collection of data — gathered through this need's assessment survey is timely, relevant, and actionable in this pandemic season or thereafter.

As yielded by the data, here are the suggested action points and recommendations the researchers suggest to further the study and maximize the use of the data gathered:

Provide programs on boosting self-esteem. Much has been harped about depression and anxiety taking hold of the studentry and a lot of guidance efforts are channeled to counseling these cases. While it is true that this area is not to be neglected, the Researchers suggest that guidance efforts on building up self-esteem be instituted or intensified if there is already a program catering to it. A lot of issues that trigger anxiety and depression are traced back to a low view of self, and a low self-esteem. It's like practicing proactivity - addressing the cause instead of wasting too much energy on reactionary plans. The researchers believe that once this is done, it will significantly help out in minimizing, if not totally preventing depression, anxiety and other mental setbacks.

Personal and Social Needs. An important step states can take to supporting students is intensifying guidance efforts in developing a program that shall encourage an open communication line between the parents and/or caregivers and the students. As what was indicated in the results of this assessment survey, a significant number of students, even if they claim to be close to their parents and/or caregivers, they claim up when it comes to opening up deep stuff of their emotions to them. Being open would significantly aid the students in processing their thoughts, feelings, and emotions in a healthy manner and will greatly help them in weeding out confusing and frustrating thoughts and emotions which often lead to depression and anxiety.

Career and Academic Needs. Even as the country plods on through the New Normal education system, the basic function of guiding the students amidst the academic challenges should be taken seriously by the academe. Strong support, guidance and encouragement on how to navigate themselves in the new normal should be closely monitored. All aspects of academic learning needs - from the technical to emotional support - should continuously be prioritized in the school guidance programs. Bearing a strong cultural Filipino psyche of regarding finishing strong in one's academic studies, the Filipino student believes that they will achieve victory in their future career when they are excelling in their studies. Strong career guidance should be formulated as well. This program shouldn't be focusing on just explaining the scope of each college course but should likewise provide proper navigation of the pros and cons of taking up a certain course and/or career path given the circumstantial facts a student has.

Spiritual Needs. Spirituality is one area where the students admitted to practicing even if some do not totally know how to practice one's faith. They believe that their faith and putting hope in God is a big factor in granting them success in their studies and carrying them through all hurdles and obstacles. Hope and faith in God are also one unique cultural trait of the Filipino and being deeply ingrained in the Filipino psyche, it would be an effective tool in motivating students and therefore deserves to occupy a significant spot in the formulation of guidance activities. Likewise, teaching the students in the practice of respecting another's spiritual beliefs would help out harmonizing the learning environment.

Critical thinking is the essence of the experience of the phenomenon, which allowed the former supporters to get rid of their cognitive dissonance and make more intelligent decisions. The existing diversities in their demographic characteristics limited the study in establishing homogeneity. Addressing the political, social, and psychological roots of increasing uncritical support for a political figure to help people be equipped to deal with it served as the study's implication.

References

- Abdulghani, F, Almelhem M, Basmaih G, Alhumud A, Alotaibi R, Wali A, Abdulghani H,. (2020). Does self-esteem lead to high achievement of the science college's students? A study from the six health science colleges. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, (27) 2, pp: 636-642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2019.11.026>.
- Adeokun, C. O., and Opoko, P. A. (2015). Exploring the Link between motivation for course-choice and retention in the architectural profession: Students' perspectives. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(6): 191-201
- Ajayi K.O., Lawani, A.O., and Salomi, M. O, (2012). —The Influences of Self Concept and Academic Motivation on Students' Attitude to Mathematics in Selected Secondary Schools in Ogun State, Nigeria,” *European Journal of Scientific Research*. Retrieved from: <http://www.sciepub.com/reference/181298>
- Aristovnik A, Keržič D, Ravšelj D, Tomažević N, Umek L. Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Life of Higher Education Students: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*. 2020; 12(20):8438. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208438>
- Arshad, M, Zaidi S., Mahmood, K. (2015). Self-Esteem & Academic Performance among University Students. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 6 (1) pp.: 156 – 162
- Atmaca, T. & Ozen, H. (2019). Self-esteem of high school students: A structural equation modelling analysis. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Science*. 14(3), pp. 422–435. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v14i3.4107>
- Aucejo, Esteban and French, Jacob and Ugalde Araya, Maria Paola and Zafar, Basit, The Impact of Covid-19 on Student Experiences

- and Expectations: Evidence from a Survey (June 2020). NBER Working Paper No. w27392, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3632618>
- Blankstein, M. (2020, March 5). Student Needs Are Academic Needs. Ithaka S+R. <https://sr.ithaka.org/publications/student-needs-are-academic-needs/>.
- Birkeland, M.S.; Melkevik, O.; Holsen, I.; Wold, B. Trajectories of global self-esteem development during adolescence. *J. Adolesc.* 2012, 35, 43–54
- Buijs, V.L., Jeronimus, B.F., Lodder, G.M.A. et al. (2021) Social Needs and Happiness: A Life Course Perspective. *J Happiness Stud* 22, 1953–1978. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-020-00287-9>
- CHAKMA, D. E. V. A. S. I. S. (2020, April 5). Needs and Importance of Personal and Social Guidance. ONLINE NOTE BANK. <https://onlinenotebank.wordpress.com/2020/04/01/needs-of-personal-and-social-guidance/>.
- Chaturvedi, K., Vishwakarma, D. K., & Singh, N. (2020, December 25). COVID-19 and its impact on education, social life and mental health of students: A survey. *Children and Youth Services Review.* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S019074092032288X>
- Cheema, G., Bhardwaj M. (2021). Study of self-esteem and academic achievement in relation to home environment among adolescents. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(1), 1978-1987.
- Clements, A.J. & Kamau, C (2018). Understanding students' motivation towards proactive career behaviours through goal-setting theory and the job demands–resources model, *Studies in Higher Education*, 43:12,2279-2293, DOI: 10.1080/03075079.2017.1326022
- Cox, C. (2011). The Relationship between Spirituality, Stress, and Academic Performance. Graduate College of Bowling Green State University.
- Crede, M., and Kuncel, N. R. (2008). Study habits, skills, and attitudes: The third pillar supporting collegiate academic performance. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3(6): 425-453.
- Cudjoe J. & Sarfo J. (2019), Improving Self-Esteem Levels among Ghanaian Junior High Students Using Designed Activities. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*. DOI: 10.13187/ejced.2019.3.483
- Darjan I., Negru M, & Ilie, D. (2020). Self-esteem – the Decisive Difference between Bullying and Assertiveness in Adolescence? *Journal of Educational Sciences*. DOI: 10.35923/JES.2020.1.0
- Deci E.L., & Ryan R.M. (2000). The —What and —Why of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior. Retrieved from: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.607.4939&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Del Castillo, F. (2020). Health, spirituality and Covid-19: Themes and insights, *Journal of Public Health*;; fdaa185, <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdaa185>
- DuBois, D.L.; Bull, C.A.; Sherman, M.D.; Roberts, M. Self-esteem and adjustment in early adolescence: A social-contextual perspective. *J. Youth Adolesc.* 1998, 27, 557–583
- D’Mello L., Monteiro, M, & Nelson P. (2018). A Study on the Self Esteem and Academic Performance among the Students. *International Journal of Health and Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)*, 2(1), 1-7
- EduNova. (2013, February 4). Improving Student Achievement: How to Improve Student Achievement. EduNova. <http://www.edunova.com/articles/student>.
- Elmer T, Mepham K, Stadtfeld C (2020) Students under lockdown: Comparisons of students' social networks and mental health before and during the COVID-19 crisis in Switzerland. *PLoS ONE* 15(7): e0236337. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0236337>
- Farhan, S., & Khan, I. (2015). Impact of stress, self-esteem and gender factor on students' academic achievement. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and their Implications*, 6(2), 143-156.
- Gesinde, A. M. (2000). Motivation. In Z.A.A. Omideyi (Editor) *Fundamental of Guidance and Counselling*. Kanead Publishers: Ibadan
- Gomez, R. & Fisher, J.W. (2003) Domains of Spiritual Well-being and Development and Validation of the Spiritual Well-Being Questionnaire Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256499063_Gomez_R_Fisher_JW_2003_
- Holopainen L., Waltzer K. , Hoang N. , Lappalainen, K. (2020). The Relationship between Students' Self-esteem, Schoolwork Difficulties and Subjective School Well-being in Finnish Upper-secondary Education. *International Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101688>
- Hull-Blanks, E., Kurpuis, S. E. R., Befort, C., Sollengberger., S., Nicpon, M.F., & Huser, L. (2005). Career Goals and Retention-related Factors Among College Freshmen. *Journal of Career Development*. Retrieved from:

- <https://asu.pure.elsevier.com/en/publications/career-goals-and-retention-relatedfactors-among-college-freshmen>
- Hyseni Duraku, Z.; Hoxha, L. Self-esteem, study skills, self-concept, social support, psychological distress, and coping mechanism effects on test anxiety and academic performance. *Health Psychol. Open* 2018, 5, 1–9 doi/10.1177/2055102918799963
- Islam MA, Barna SD, Raihan H, Khan MNA, Hossain MT (2020) Depression and anxiety among university students during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh: A web-based cross-sectional survey. *PLoS ONE* 15(8): e0238162. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238162>
- Jorgenson, D. A., Farrell, L. C., Fudge, J. L., & Pritchard, A. (2018). College Connectedness: The Student Perspective. *Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 75-95.
- Kanwal, W. (2006). Impact of locus of control and self-esteem on the academic achievement orientations of private and public sector university students. (Doctoral dissertation) at National University of Modern Languages (NUML) Islamabad.
- Kecojevic A, Basch CH, Sullivan M, Davi NK (2020) The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on mental health of undergraduate students in New Jersey, cross-sectional study. *PLoS ONE* 15(9): e0239696. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0239696
- Kharsah, W. & Latada, F. (2016). The Correlation between Levels of Self-Esteem, University Commitment and Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students. *The National Conference for Postgraduate Research 2016*, Universiti Malaysia Pahang.
- Koenig H. G. (2012). Religion, spirituality, and health: the research and clinical implications. *ISRN psychiatry*, 2012, 278730. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2012/278730>
- Kroth, Michael 2007. "Maslow—Move aside! A Heuristical Motivation Model for Leaders in Career and Technical Education." *Journal of Industrial Teacher Education* 44 (2): 5-36.
- Lee, J. (2020, April 14). Mental health effects of school closures during COVID-19. *THE LANCET Child and Adolescent Health*. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanchi/article/PIIS2352-4642\(20\)30109-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanchi/article/PIIS2352-4642(20)30109-7/fulltext).
- Lewison, K. (2020, May 19). Focusing On Student Well-Being In Times Of Crisis. University of the People. <https://www.uopeople.edu/blog/student-well-being-in-times-of-crisis/>.
- Linderman, A. J. (2010). Seventh grade student career aspirations and academic achievement. *Counselor Education Master's Theses* 67. Retrieved from http://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/edc_theses/67.
- Lopez-Bonilla, J. M., Barrera, R. B., Serrano, M. A. R., Lopez-Bonilla, L. M., Florencio, B. P., and Rodriguez, M. C. R. (2012). Reasons which influence students' decisions to take a university course: Differences by gender and degree. *Educational Studies*, 38(3): 297-310.
- Maheswari, R. & Maheswari, K. (2016). A Study on Self-Esteem Among the College Students. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*: 21: 10: 08-10 doi: 10.9790/08372110080810
- Maslow, Abraham 1964. *Religions, Values, and Peak-experiences* (Penguin ed.,1976). New York: Penguin Books.
- Maunder, R. E. (2017). Students' peer relationships and their contribution to university adjustment: the need to belong in the university community. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 756-768.
- Moriya, K. (2011). Why is career education so important? *PsycEXTRA Dataset*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e605292012-011>
- Mosanya, M. (2020, October 16). Buffering Academic Stress during the COVID-19 Pandemic Related Social Isolation: Grit and Growth Mindset as Protective Factors against the Impact of Loneliness. *International Journal of Applied Positive Psychology*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s41042-020-00043-7>.
- Mustafa, S. & Mustafa, A. (2017). Importance of Career Planning and Development in Education. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*. doi:10.23918/ijsses.v4i2sip149
- National Center for Education Statistics. (2021). Students' Internet Access Before and During the Coronavirus Pandemic by Household Socioeconomic Status. NCES. <https://nces.ed.gov/blogs/nces/post/students-internet-access-before-and-during-the-coronavirus-pandemic-by-household-socioeconomic-status>
- Nicholas Grubic, S. B. (2020, May 2). Student mental health in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic: A call for further research and immediate solutions - Nicholas Grubic, Shaylea Badovinac, Amer M Johri, 2020. *SAGE Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0020764020925108>.
- Nieve, M., Alberto, Q. & Alejandra, P. (2020). Self-Esteem and Motivation for Learning in Academic Achievement: The Mediating Role of Reasoning and Verbal Fluidity. doi:10.3390/su12145768
- Orth, U., & Robins, R. W. (2014). The development of self-esteem. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 23(5), 381-387.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721414547414>

Pedrosa, A. L., Bitencourt, L., Fróes, A. C. F., Cazumbá, M. L. B., Campos, R. G. B., de Brito, S. B. C. S., & Simões e Silva, A. C. (2020, September 10). Emotional, Behavioral, and Psychological Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Frontiers*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.566212/full>.

Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2020). RESET and REBUILD for a Better Philippines in the Post-Pandemic World. PIDS. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsepm2020-2021.pdf>

Puchalski, C., Vitillo, R., Hull, S. & Reller, N. (2014). "Improving the spiritual dimension of whole person care: Reaching national and international consensus". *Journal of Palliative Medicine* 17:642–56.

Roman, N. V., Mthembu, T. G., & Hoosen, M. (2020). Spiritual care - 'A deeper immunity' - A response to Covid-19 pandemic. *African journal of primary health care & family medicine*, 12(1), e1–e3. <https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v12i1.2456>

Saladino, V., Algeri, D., & Auriemma, V. (2020, September 3). The Psychological and Social Impact of Covid-19: New Perspectives of Well-Being. *Frontiers*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.577684/full>.

Schleicher, A. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Education: Insights from Education at a Glance 2020. *Education at a Glance*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/69096873-en>

Schoon, I., and Polek, E. (2011). Teenage career aspirations and adult career attainment: The role of gender, social background and general cognitive ability. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 35(3): 210–217

Sherwin, Sarah, and Liz Stevenson 2010. "Creating an Optimum Environment for Learning." *British Journal of School Nursing* 5 (9): 455-457.

Sheykhjan, T., Jabari K, and Rajeswari., (2014). Self-esteem and Academic Achievement of High School Students. *Cognitive Discourses International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(2). Retrieved from: <http://cdimj.naspublishers.com>

Son C, Hegde S, Smith A, Wang X, Sasangohar (2020). Effects of COVID-19 on College Students' Mental Health in the United States: Interview Survey Study *J Med Internet Res* 2020;22(9):e21279 URL: <https://www.jmir.org/2020/9/e21279DOI:10.2196/21279>

Stefa, E. (2018). Supportive Relationship between Teachers and Students and Among Peers. *European Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*.

Trinidad, J. E., & Leviste, E. N. P. (2020). Toward greater access and impact: Directions for a sociological understanding of Philippine higher education. *Industry and Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422220954062>

Torres, Adam A. (2007) "Relationships Between Self-Esteem and Factors Known to Affect College Attendance," *McNair Scholars Research Journal*: Vol. 3: Issue 1, Article 13. Available at: https://scholarworks.boisestate.edu/mcnair_journal/vol3/iss1/13

Tsurugano, S, Nishikitani, M, Inoue, M, Yano, E. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on working students: Results from the Labour Force Survey and the student lifestyle survey. *J Occup Health*. 2021; 63:e12209. <https://doi.org/10.1002/1348-9585.12209>

Ümmet, D. (2015) Self-esteem among college students: a study of satisfaction of basic psychological needs and some variables. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*: 174: 1623 – 1629 doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.813

Vahedi, S. H., & Ghani-Zadeh, S. (2009). Analysis of the Relationship between Internal Religious Motivation, Prayer (Namaz), Spiritual Well-Being, Quality of Life and Psychological Well-being of Students. *Journal of Psychological Health*, 2(10), 7-24. from: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/nvsm.%2031/abstract%20Vahedi,%20S>

Waithaka, A. G., Furniss, T. M., & Gitimu, P. N. (2017). College Student Mind-Set: Does Student-Parental Relationship Influences the Student's Mind-Set? *Research in Higher Education Journal*, 16.

Waseem, J. 2020. Regression Model on Self-Esteem, Self-Efficacy, Locus of Control as Predictors of Academic Performance of students in Higher Education. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22555/joeeed.v7i2.6>

Wasylikiw, L., Hanson, S., Lynch, L., Vaillancourt, Wilson E. (2021). Predicting undergraduate student outcomes: Competing or complementary roles of self-esteem, self-compassion, self-efficacy, and mindsets? *Vol 50 No 2 (2020): 50(2)*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47678/cjhe.v50i2.188679>

William, O.-B., & Isaac, O. O. (2016). Student Spirituality and Academic Performance: A Case Study of Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), Ghana. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 17(4), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.9734/BJESBS/2016/27910>

Wong, D. W., Hall, K. R., Justice, C. A., & Hernandez, L. W. (2015). Counseling individuals through the lifespan.

Wood J.L. & Hilton A.A. (2012). Spirituality and academic success: Perceptions of African American males in the community college.

Religion & Education.39(1):28-47.

Yorke, L., Rose, P., Bayley, S., Meshesha, D. W., & Ramchandani, P. (2021, March). The Importance of Students' Socio-Emotional Learning, Mental Health, and Wellbeing in the Time of COVID-19. RISE Programme. <https://riseprogramme.org/publications/importance-students-socio-emotional-learning-mental-health-and-wellbeing-time-covid-19>.

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